

Studies in the Synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives: Part I: Synthesis of Bromoquinolines

R. J. Chudgar and K. N. Trivedi

Bromination of acetoacetanilide gave ω -bromo-acetoacetanilide, the structure of which was proved by NMR spectra and also by its cyclisation to 4-bromomethyl-carbostyryl which was different from 4-methyl-3-bromo-carbostyryl. Several substituted acetoacetarylamides were brominated to ω -bromo derivative which underwent cyclisation to 4-bromomethylcarbostyryl derivatives. 3-Bromo-4-methyl-carbostyryl derivatives and 3-bromo-4-bromomethylcarbostyryl were also prepared.

Knorr¹ brominated acetoacetanilide in chloroform solution and claimed to have obtained α -bromoacetoacetanilide. Hasegawa² and Cook *et al.*³ repeated the above experiment in chloroform and regarded the product as ω -bromoacetoacetanilide (I). Mehta and coworkers^{4,5} brominated acetoacetanilide in acetic acid and claimed to have obtained α -bromo-acetoacetanilide. They further claimed that this product on cyclisation gave 3-bromo-4-methyl-carbostyryl (II) which was identical with the product obtained on bromination of 4-methyl-carbostyryl (III). In view of these contradictory reports, it was thought of interest to repeat the work by both the procedures. In both the cases, however, the same product was obtained, which is assigned ω -bromoacetoacetanilide structure (I) as it gave on cyclisation 4-bromo-methylcarbostyryl (IV). The latter was different from the 3-bromo-4-methylcarbostyryl (II) obtained by bromination of 4-methylcarbostyryl (III). 4-Bromomethyl-carbostyryl (IV) on reduction with zinc and acetic acid gave the known 4-methylcarbostyryl (III). The structure of ω -bromoacetoacetanilide (I) was further confirmed by its NMR spectra and also by its conversion to known 2-hydroxyquinchoninic acid⁶.

In a similar manner a series of compounds are prepared from the substituted acetoacetanilides. Further bromination of 4-bromomethylcarbostyryl afforded 4-bromomethyl-3-bromocarbostyryl which was also obtained from 4-methylcarbostyryl on treatment with excess of N-bromosuccinimide.

1. L. Knorr, *Ann.*, 1886, **236**, 79.
2. M. Hasegawa, *Pharm. Bull.*, 1953, **1**, 50.
3. D. J. Cook, R. Bowen, P. Sorter and E. Daniels, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 4949.
4. C. M. Mehta, J. M. Trivedi and G. H. Patel, *J. Sci. and Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 460.
5. C. M. Mehta and G. H. Patel, *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, **30**, 15.
6. R. J. Chudgar and K. N. Trivedi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1965, **34**, 560.

NMR Spectra of ω -bromoacetoacetanilide (I)(56.445 MC/s $CDCl_3$)

Shift (δ)	Signals	Assignment
9.21	Singlet	-NH-
7.27	Multiplet	5H (Aromatic)
4.06	Singlet	Br-CH ₂ -CO
3.79	Singlet	CO-CH ₂ -CO

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedures :

Bromination of acetoacetarylamides : The anilide (0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of hot glacial acetic acid and bromine in acetic acid (10%; 0.01 mole) was added and left overnight. Some bromo compounds (Table 1) separated on standing while others were

TABLE 1

S.No.	ω -bromoderivative of acetoacet-	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %	
				Required	Found
1.	<i>p</i> -toluidide	148	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	Br = 29.63	29.61
2.	<i>p</i> -chloroanilide	130	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NBrCl	C = 41.31	41.71
				H = 3.09	3.41
				N = 4.82	4.64
3.	<i>m</i> -chloroanilide	97.9	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NBrCl	C = 41.31	41.61
				H = 3.09	3.32
				N = 4.82	4.52
4.	<i>p</i> -bromoanilide	126.8	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NBr ₂	Br = 47.76	47.49
5.	1 : 3 : 4-xylidide	97	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	Br = 28.17	28.28
6.	<i>o</i> -toluidide ^a	85 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	Br = 29.63	29.45
7.	<i>p</i> -anisidide	138	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃ NBr	Br = 27.97	28.11
8.	α -naphthylamide	237 d	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	Br = 26.19	26.00
9.	<i>p</i> -phenetidide	147.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ NBr	Br = 26.66	26.40

^a reported bromination in chloroform which gave thick oil.

obtained on dilution with water. They were crystallised either from alcohol or dilute acetic acid. The same bromo derivatives were obtained when bromination was carried out with bromine in chloroform.

4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl derivatives : The above ω -bromo derivative (3 g.) was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (6 ml.) and heated on water bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 hr. It was poured over ice water and the separated product (Table 2) was filtered and crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid.

TABLE 2

S.No.	Substituent in 4-bromomethyl carbostyryl	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	Analysis %	
				Required	Found
1.	6-methyl	265	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBr	Br = 31.75	32.00
2.	6-chloro	247	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONBrCl	C = 44.03	44.44
				H = 2.56	2.51
				N = 5.13	4.99
3.	7-chloro	261-2	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONBrCl	C = 44.03	44.34
				H = 2.56	2.71
				N = 5.13	4.92
4.	6-bromo	278	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONBr ₂	Br = 50.47	50.17
5.	6-8-dimethyl	254	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONBr	Br = 30.08	30.53
6.	8-methyl	241	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBr	Br = 31.75	32.00
7.	6-methoxy	250-1	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ NBr	Br = 29.85	30.04
8.	7,8-benzo	249	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ONBr	Br = 27.79	27.99
9.	6-ethoxy	257	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	Br = 28.37	28.03

Reduction with zinc and acetic acid : The above 4-bromomethylcarbostyryl derivative (0.5 g.) was refluxed with zinc (1 g.) and acetic acid (5 ml.) for 45–60 min. It was filtered hot and the filtrate on cooling gave 4-methylcarbostyryl derivative. The mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared by cyclisation of corresponding acetoacetylamide was not depressed.

Bromination of 4-methylcarbostyryl : 4-Methylcarbostyryl (0.01 mole) dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid was treated with bromine in acetic acid (10%; 0.01 mole) and left overnight. The separated product (Table 3) was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid.

TABLE 3

S.No.	Substituent in 3-bromo-4-methyl-carbostyryl	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	Analysis %	
				Required	Found
1.	6-methyl	294	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBr	Br = 31.75	31.48
2.	6-chloro	273	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONBrCl	C = 44.10	44.56
				H = 2.57	2.98
				N = 5.14	5.08
3.	7-chloro	298	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONBrCl	C = 44.10	44.14
				H = 2.57	2.42
				N = 5.14	4.76
4.	6-bromo	303	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONBr ₂	Br = 50.47	50.03
5.	6,8-dimethyl	272	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONBr	Br = 30.09	30.11

4-Bromomethyl-3-bromocarbostyryl: 4-Methylcarbostyryl (1.0 g.) suspended in chloroform (30 ml.) was treated with N-bromosuccinimide (3 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 7-8 hr. The separated product was filtered and the residue washed with acetic acid and water. The product was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 303°. Mixed m.p. with the product obtained by the bromination of 4-bromomethylcarbostyryl was not depressed. (Found: Br = 50.42. C₁₀H₇ONBr₂ requires Br = 50.47%).

Our grateful thanks are due to Dr. C. R. Kanekar of the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bombay for the NMR Spectra and helpful discussions regarding its interpretation. Thanks are also due to Professor S. Sethna for his interest in the work and to Dr. Lele for microanalysis.

Chemistry Department,
Faculty of Science,
M.S. University of Baroda,
Baroda.

Received September 24, 1968.